

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE MANIFESTATION OF GENDER RELATIONS IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. This article studies the specific features of the manifestation of gender relations in the family. It discusses the theoretical and practical aspects of this problem, as well as scientific research carried out by world psychologists in this regard. The research conducted by the author shows that the study of this problem is still very relevant today.

Keywords: society, family, marriage, gender relations, gender equality, men, women, oppression, violence.

If we look at the historical roots of the family, in our country the family has always been highly valued as a sacred institution. Its preservation, preventing the destruction of this sacred institution has always been the constant focus of our society, and this value retains its importance today. In particular, with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated February 18, 2020 “On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the makhalla institution, and bring the system of work with the family and women to a new level”, family values and the family institution have entered a new stage of development. One of the main tasks set for the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, established at the initiative of our Head of State, is to reveal the historical roots of the family institution and develop family values. In this regard, over the past period, our state has been carrying out a lot of practical work to strengthen families in our country, especially young families who are just starting to enter the threshold of adulthood, and to help them develop independently as part of society.

Article 76 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that “The family is the basic unit of society and is under the protection of society and the state.” Also, in accordance with Article 2 of the “Family Code” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is established that the regulation of family relations shall be carried out on the basis of the principles of a voluntary union of a man and a woman, equality of personal and property rights of husband and wife, resolution of internal family issues by mutual agreement, priority of raising children in the family, caring for their well-being and maturity, and protection of the rights and interests of minor and incapable family members. During the ongoing reforms, it

is appropriate to further improve the legal framework for the family, taking into account the specific aspects of our society and based on an analysis of the legislative experience of developed countries in the world, and to create a solid foundation for our future.

One of the main manifestations of the development of society is the existence of a system of equal rights and equal opportunities between representatives of both sexes. If gender equality is not ensured in a society, there will be no development in that society, because when the rights of women and men are violated, inequality arises in the social life of that society, labor productivity decreases, economic growth slows down, children are born unhealthy, and the level of poverty increases. Therefore, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-562 dated September 2, 2019 "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" establishes the provision of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, regulation of relations in the field. However, despite the existence of a legal framework, it is true that many girls and women in our country face discrimination related to gender equality, and unfortunately, there are also cases of women not contacting law enforcement agencies or relevant organizations when they experience various forms of violence or oppression against women in the family. In such cases, women are forced to absorb the violence inflicted on them. This leads to psychological stress, physical and spiritual oppression of a person. The fact that such negative situations in families do not decrease today indicates that this situation remains a topical issue that requires separate study and the need to intensify scientific research on it.

It is noteworthy that the study of the socio-psychological characteristics of the manifestation of gender equality in interpersonal relationships in the family was studied in the last years of the last century by E. Clarared in Switzerland, T. Schreiber in Germany; R. Jane, A. Willi, E. Dlorkate in France; K. Buehler, S. Hall, W. James, D. Dobson, J. Bruler, L. Morgan in America; G. M. Andreyeva, B. Malinovsky, M. Kovalevsky, R. Sorokin, A. Kharshev, N. N. Obozov, S. I. Golod, N. N. Bogomolova, A. Adler, A. I. Antonov, L. Y. Gozman, T. M. Mishina, S. Minukhin, S. V. Kovalev in the Russian Federation; and psychologists from Central Asian countries B. Polvonova, M. Beysenova, M. Rakhimova and others.

Z. Freud believes that "any violence or any type or form of violence is caused by an excess of aggressive energy" [3]. According to him, internal energy accumulates in a person and reaches a dangerous level, and if it is difficult to release it, a state of catharsis can help. Catharsis in real, normal situations is the

expenditure of energy in games that require various forces (for example, a football game) or when watching these games. Supporters of Freudian psychoanalysts emphasize that if a child participates in sports games at school or is passionately involved in sports, they will not develop aggression, in contrast to a child who does not participate in anything else and is passive. Freudians also point out that violent, aggressive criminals (hostile aggression) have similarly strained their power and excitement, unable to release the energy, and when they could not control it, an "explosion" occurred, which turned into a form of violent aggression.

Rolf Leber and Magda Stutzhammer-Leber advise researchers studying aggression to: remember whether aggressive actions are overt or covert. According to Rolf Leber and Magda Stutzhammer-Leber, the psychological foundations of these gender relations are, in turn, divided into the following types: 1) Pattern behavior; 2) Emotions; 3) Cognitive processes; 4) Development. Violation of gender relations in an overt form is a direct, open attack on the victim in behavior, causing physical harm and harm. In a covert form, it is hidden in its name, through gossip, rumors, deception, lies, etc. In most cases, overt aggression weakens with age, becomes hidden, and covert aggression increases. However, if overt aggression is very strongly developed in childhood, they may also commit violent crimes when they grow up, for example, aggression related to private property [5].

M. Flood and L. Fergus note that the impact of domestic violence on children also has significant consequences. Children are likely to hear or witness domestic violence, and this situation affects them in the following ways:

- 1) affects the neural pathways of the brain that affect cognitive development and stress response systems;
- 2) causes difficulties in self-esteem and social relationships at school;
- 3) affects financial security;
- 4) mental health problems, including anxiety, depression, eating disorders and, in some cases, suicide attempts;
- 5) increased likelihood of aggression, antisocial behavior and drug use;
- 6) causes problems such as early pregnancy [4].

Our scientific research work, slightly different from the scientific research of the above-mentioned scientists, is aimed at studying the cases of oppression and violence in interpersonal relationships in Uzbek families. For this, 145 respondents from Kashkadarya region and 144 from Surkhandarya region, a total of 289 respondents, were involved in the experimental work. In our study,

R. Lazarus's "Manifestation of aggressive behavior" methodology was used. The intended goal was to determine how the empirical results obtained through the methodology, based on the manifestation of individual behavior in a husband or wife during the period of domestic violence, arise in the family in relation to the violation of the cycle of family-marital relations, how the motives for the use of physical force by the husband against his wife arise, and what negative qualities and (or) violations of values are the dominant manifestations in this.

Table 1

Analysis of results according to R. Lazarus's "Coping Behavioral Manifestations" methodology (n=289)

Scales	Gender	M	σ	t
Confrontational coping	Male n=143	42,3	2,7	-0,93
	Woman n=146	41,9	3,0	
Keep your distance	Male n= 143	39,2	3,0	-3,03*
	Woman n=146	43,5	3,3	
Self-control	Male n= 143	44,2	3,2	0,76
	Woman n=146	43,1	2,9	
Seeking social support	Male n=143	40,3	3,1	-4,53*
	Woman n=146	46,2	2,5	
Accepting responsibility	Male n=143	45,3	2,3	-3,28*
	Woman n=146	41,7	3,0	
Self-isolation – criteria	Male n=143	39,8	3,1	-2,23*
	Woman n=146	43,2	2,8	
Planning to solve the problem	Male n=143	43,3	2,8	-1,03
	Woman n=146	42,6	2,7	
Positive evaluation	Male n=143	38,2	3,2	0,39
	Woman n=146	39,5	3,0	

Note: * $p \leq 0,05$; *** $p \leq 0,001$.

The results of the methodology, modified based on the requirements of the R. Lazarus coping test, made it possible to obtain relevant empirical data on the coping behavior of a particular person in a stressful situation. After all, the interpretation of the obtained data makes it possible to know the perceptions of coping behavior in family relationships and, through these perceptions, to determine the correct psychological approach to each family member.

No differences were observed in the objects of the study among the initial, “confrontational coping” factor ($t=-0.93$, $p\leq 0.37$). Based on the analysis of the studied theoretical data, we can say that any coping behavior is associated with the phenomenon of the personality, which includes the “I-concept”, locus of control, reflection, empathy, etc. All of them together constitute the stable characteristics of the personality, and these processes form such characteristics as socialization, behavior management, and all internal approval or disapproval of the personality. The naming of the personality character has a significant impact on the selection of strategies used to eliminate an unpleasant event, and the result of the activity will be similar.

The next factor, “keeping distance,” showed significant differences ($t=-3.03^*$, $p\leq 0.05$). This factor showed a higher result in women. It was observed that in various problematic situations in family relationships and internal conflicts, women often isolate their own problems and try to forget about them. In men, it was found that the qualities of focusing on the emotional aspect of the subjective significance of the problem in overcoming negative thoughts and fantasies related to it are relatively lower.

No differences were observed in the research objects among the next factor in the methodology, “self-control” ($t=0.76$, $p\leq 0.24$). This indicates that in both research groups, the characteristics of focusing on the problem-solving process and keeping negative emotions under control, choosing behavioral strategies and minimizing their impact on the perception of the situation, and striving to maintain high control over oneself are almost identical.

Significant differences were noted in the factor “seeking social support” ($t=-4.53^*$, $p\leq 0.05$) of our methodology. The characteristics such as striving to solve the problem with the help of external (social) resources, i.e., seeking informational, emotional, practical support, orientation towards interaction with people, expecting encouragement, attention, advice, sympathy, and specific practical help from them showed a high result in women. In men, it was found that the attitude towards expecting vital, material, and emotional support from society was at a lower level.

The next factor, “accepting responsibility,” also showed significant differences ($t=-3.28^*$, $p\leq 0.05$). This means that men tend to avoid repeating their previous mistakes, to blame themselves for the problems they face, to criticize themselves in specific components, and to be dissatisfied with themselves.

The next factor of the methodology used in the study, “self-isolation”, showed a higher result in women than in men ($t=-2.23^*$, $p\leq 0.05$). In individuals

of this type, the tendency to fantasy in stressful situations, a pronounced infantile form of behavior in the strategy of avoiding problems, and the desire to isolate oneself from problematic situations in various interpersonal relationships showed a higher result in women than in men.

No significant differences were observed in the last factor of the methodology, “planning to solve the problem” ($t=-1.03$, $p\leq 0.32$) and “positive assessment” ($t=0.39$, $p\leq 0.29$). This indicates that there are certain similarities in the characteristics of couples in family relationships, such as analyzing problematic situations, developing specific plans to overcome them, using positive terms in overcoming difficulties, interpreting them and accepting them positively by the individual, developing a problem-solving strategy, using previously acquired experience and resources, and drawing up a personal work plan under objective conditions.

In conclusion, a person's coping behavior in stressful situations is to a certain extent important for the response to stressful situations. This is especially important in conflicts that may arise in family relationships. Taking this into account, it was intended to empirically study the socio-psychological factors associated with the correlation between coping behavior and response to stressful situations in women and men in the family and analyze its results on the basis of conditionally accepted criteria. It is also worth noting that sometimes each person experiences certain difficulties in adequately assessing their capabilities in stressful situations. In our opinion, the basis of such difficulties can be explained by the lack of sufficient understanding of stressful situations.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi (Yangi tahriri): https://constitution.uz/uploads/constitution_uz.pdf
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Oila kodeksi: (2021 yil 1 martgacha bo‘lgan o‘zgartish va qo‘shimchalar bilan) Rasmiy nashr - O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Adliya vazirligi. - T.: “Adolat”, 2021. -208 b.
3. Фрейд З. Семейный роман невротиков / Зигмунд Фрейд. – Москва: Азбука, 2023. -224 с.
4. Flood M., Fergus L.2008, An Assault on Our Future: The impact of violence on young people and their relationships//<https://eprints.qut.edu.au/103828/1/qut.edu.au Documents StaffHome staffgroup B% 24 bozzetto Documents 2017001017.pdf>

5. Loeber, R., Lahey, B. B., & Thomas, C. (1991). Diagnostic conundrum of oppositional defiant disorder and conduct disorder. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 100(3), 379–390, Stanger, Achenbach & Verhulst, 1997.

